

Neo-Realism in Thai's Film after Political Crisis in October 14, 1973 and Political Crisis between 2005-2014

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Abstract : The objective of presenting this article is to analyze between Thai's film and Thai society in political crisis, to study the development and trend of the film which reflects society in Thailand from political crisis of 14 October 1973 and the present day political crisis using a comparative study of the two era, both the similarities and differences in the film reflects the society in an era of change.

Keywords : film, political, neo-realism, social, Thailand

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